

Figure S1. The sequence alignment and primer information of *GbTMEM214s*. The alignment was performed with MEGA 5 software and visualized with GeneDoc software. The alignment for VIGS were marked with shadows of different colors. The primers for qRT-PCR were marked with different color boxes. The termination codons in coding

sequences were marked with yellow shadows.